

PRELIMINARY STUDY ON MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF BACTERIAL CELLULOSE/PVA MULTILAYER COMPOSITE HYDROGELS

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Keywords: *composite hydrogels; bacterial cellulose; polyvinyl alcohol; mechanical properties*

1 Introduction

Polymer hydrogels used to replace damaged tissues is a promising incentive for their good biocompatibility in contact with human tissues. Crosslinked polyvinyl alcohol hydrogels (PVA-H) are a class of viscoelastic materials with high water contents, and possess good biocompatibility, high elasticity and good chemical stability and durability, which are promising substitute biomaterials for soft and tough tissue, such as articular cartilage, artery, ligament etc[1]. However, the low bulk modulus and limited biomechanical properties of hydrogels hinder the further development of their bio-medical applications. A lot of materials have compounded with PVA hydrogels in order to improve their mechanical properties, including hydroxylapatite, chitosan etc[2,3]. But the lack of good matching mechanical properties between some natural tissue, such as meniscus, and the PVA hydrogels is still an open issue.

Bacterial cellulose (BC) has a wide range of applications, particularly in medical field, including artificial skin, microvessels, wound dressings, and scaffold for tissue engineering, due to its high purity, the ultrafine network architecture, high hydrophilicity, and excellent biocompatibility, produced by zymolysis using *Acetobacter xylinum*[4]. Recently, BC has been effectively used as a reinforcement to improve the mechanical performance of the composites[5]. However, most of these composites were prepared by using only the BC nanofibres but not BC gel membranes as a component. There are no reports so far about the research on using the BC gel to reinforce hydrogel. In this work, a new kind of multilayer composite hydrogels was designed and prepared by compounding several layers of BC gel membranes with PVA hydrogels. The mechanical properties and microstructures of BC/PVA composite hydrogel with different water content and weight percent were tested and compared.

2 Materials and Method

Bacterial cellulose, with three-dimensional network of nano and microfibrils with 10~100nm width, was

supplied by YIDA CO., LTD (China). One commercially available polyvinyl alcohol with degree of polymerization of 1750 was used in this work. PVA particles were dissolved into the distilled water completely with continuously stirring for hours at the temperature of 80°C. Pretreated BC gel membranes were dipped into PVA solution with different weight percent for a few minutes. Subsequently, several layers of BC gel membranes were overlaying onto PVA colloid solution, and gelating by method of repeating freezing-thawing to make the multilayer composite hydrogels. The mechanical property of the composite hydrogels was tested by Autograph Mechanical Tester (Rising Sun Testing instruments Co.Ltd, China). Micro-morphology and microstructures of the interface between PVA-H and BC gel membranes were observed by scanning electron microscopy (SEM).

3 Results and Discussion

3.1 Morphology of BC/PVA composite hydrogels

Fig.1. Schematic diagram of the multilayer composite hydrogels

BC/PVA multilayer composite hydrogels were designed and prepared by overlaying several layers of BC gel membranes onto PVA gel as shown in Fig1. The electron scanning micrographs in Fig2 was the morphology of connective interface between PVA-H and BC gel membrane. Fig2(a) showed the lateral morphology of the composite hydrogels and indicated the close combination between BC gel membranes with the low water content and PVA with the mass percent of 15% (wt). The different layers of

BC, water content and gel formation conditions influenced the combination between BC and PVA. Fig2(b) was the interface morphology by separating PVA from BC, and presented the intercrossed microstructure of two macro-molecules by PVA colloid infiltrating and gelating into the nanofibrils network of BC gel membrane, which meant the excellent combination of BC and PVA during the formation of composite gels.

Fig.2. SEM of the connection for BC/PVA composite hydrogels (a) lateral morphology, (b) interface morphology

3.2 Mechanical properties

There are many factors which influence the mechanical properties of BC/PVA hydrogels, including PVA contents, different layers of BC, water content, as well as gel formation conditions. The close and deep-set combination between BC and PVA results in a significant increase in the mechanical properties. Fig3(a) showed tensile stress/strain curves of BC/PVA composite hydrogels with different water content. Fig3(b) showed the elastic modulus varying with the different layers of BC and PVA mass percent. It could be seen that the elastic modulus and rigidity of the composite hydrogels increased with the decrease of water content of hydrogel, as well as the increase of layers of BC. This was owing to the reinforcement of BC gel membranes PVA hydrogels through the intercross and infiltration of the two macromolecules.

4 Conclusions

BC/PVA multilayer composite hydrogels were prepared by overlaying several layers of BC gel membranes onto PVA colloid solution and gelating by method of repeating freezing-thawing. The different layers of BC, water content and gel formation conditions influenced the combination between BC gel membrane and PVA, sequentially resulted in the changes of mechanical properties. BC gel membrane acted as a strong reinforcement to enhance the elastic modulus, strength and rigidity of the composite hydrogel.

Fig.3. Tensile stress-strain curves (a) and the elastic modulus (b) of the composite hydrogels with various components

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